

FADAMA III DEVELOPMENT PROJECT AND REHABILITATION OF COMMUNITY OWNED AGRICULTURAL INFRASTRUCTURE IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study seeks to examine the impact of Fadama III on the rehabilitation of community owned agricultural infrastructure in Akwa Ibom State. It was observed that the agricultural sector after independence, dominated the Nigerian economy, such that the development of the region was hinged on the sector alone. However, over the years, the sector has witnessed rapid decline in its role and contribution to national development. The National Fadama Development Project (NFDP) is one of such intervention program that was initiated to improve the agricultural sector of the country. The Theory of change and the group theory were used for the study. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The sources of data were both primary and secondary. Primary data were sourced using a questionnaire and interview method. Secondary data were sourced from textbooks, journal publications, and online sources. The population of the study was 2730 Fadama users in Akwa Ibom State. Using the Taro Yamane formula, a Sample size of 400 was determined and administered, out of which 354 were successfully retrieved. The Simple linear regression analysis was the method of data analysis. It was revealed that there is a significant relationship between Fadama III and rehabilitation of community owned agricultural infrastructure in Akwa Ibom State. The study recommended that; Akwa Ibom State government should ensure that agricultural infrastructure left uncompleted, abandoned or dysfunctional should be resuscitated and made fully operational to increase the scope and scale of food production in the state.

Keywords: Agriculture development, Agricultural Infrastructure, Fadama III and Rehabilitation.

Introduction

In sub-Saharan Africa, agriculture occupies a prominent position in the national economies, as the sector serves as a key driver of growth, wealth creation, employment as well as poverty reduction. According to Affias, Anwana and Umohudo (2018), it is also the leading economic activity in the continent which contributes between 20 % and 30 % of its Gross Domestic Product. In an agrarian economy like Nigeria, the land as a unit for agricultural production provides the needed fulcrum upon which a sustainable development would blossom. Agricultural production till date remains the mainstay of the Nigerian

economy. With a population that is largely agrarian, agriculture has traditionally been the main sources of livelihood for our people. It provides the means of livelihood for over 70 % of the population and a major source of raw materials for the agro-allied industries and potent source of the much needed foreign exchange (Ogunrinola and Osahbuohien, 2010).

Thus, the importance of agricultural development in generating employment and stimulating overall economic development in a developing country such as Nigeria cannot be undermined. Most public policies in Nigeria, especially since independence are tailored towards promoting food security, provision of the agricultural raw materials needed by the manufacturing sector to provide adequate employment and income to alleviate poverty as well as earn substantial foreign exchange. Depicts this milestone, over the years there is a decreasing desire for agricultural development in Nigeria particularly in rural areas of Nigeria and by extension, Akwa Ibom state. The problem of agriculture development in Nigeria has been an issue of concern to different tiers of government due to the alarming rate of food scarcity and rural poverty.

According to Ekan, Imoh-Ita and Ntuen, (2024) agriculture development is faced with the paradox that the development-oriented economy relies heavily on non-productive Agriculture Infrastructures and equipment with outdated tools, lack of technical information, and lack of scientific and cultural training. These factors have made international organizations like the World Bank and other donor agencies embark upon some programmes, like Fadama Projects in collaboration with developing nations including Nigeria aiming to improve the standards of agriculture infrastructures (Olawepo, 2010). The Fadama project is a World Bank development programme which collaborates with the Nigerian government. The National Fadama Development Project (NFDP) which has been executed in three phases-Fadama I, II, and III. The current Fadama III project is designed to increase the production efficiency of Fadama users (farmers, pastoralists, hunters, among others) and consequently their incomes, produces yield and infrastructures (Olaolu *et al.*, 2012). According to Iwala (2014), Fadama is a Hausa word for wetland, internationally accepted in soil science literature as wetland soils or hydromorphic soils which are the seasonally or permanently poor drained soils of river valleys and flood plains of the coastal and Delta swamps. These productive soils can be utilized in both wet and dry seasons.

Statement of the Problem

The agricultural sector after independence, dominated the Nigerian economy, such that the development of the region was hinged on the sector alone. Agriculture accounted for about two-thirds of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). However, over the years, the sector has witnessed rapid decline in its role and contribution to national development (Ogbalubi & Wokocha, 2013). Hoes have been abandoned in pursuit of the black gold. This situation started with the "Oil boom" which led to the rapid decline of the Agricultural sector. Consequently, Nigeria became a major importer of agricultural products as against its earlier position as a major exporter. This led to a decline of the economically active population in agriculture in Nigeria as well as an increase in the level of unemployment.

Development economists have in fact noted that the present agriculture situation in the country to the poor performance of the agricultural sector is that the majority of farmers in Nigeria are engaged in primitive and traditional methods of agricultural production which is caused by poor agriculture infrastructure (Ogunmuyiwa & Adelowokan, 2018). The near eclipse of the sector in the era of oil boom (1972- 1975), has been described as the most

serious damage done to agricultural sector in Nigeria. The socio economic and production characteristics of the farmers, inconsistent and unfocused government policies as well as inadequate infrastructural base (road networking/bad transportation system), all combined to choke the sector, resulting in low production and consequently high prices of food items.

In attempt to curtail this societal problem in the agricultural sector to ensure food sufficiency and the reduction of poverty occasioned by poor performance of agriculture sector, the government of Nigeria has introduced various agricultural programs, policies and projects aimed at encouraging mass involvement in agriculture. The National Fadama Development Project (NFDP) is one of such intervention program. The National Fadama Development Project (NFDP) has been executed in three phases – Fadama I, II, and III so far. Our concern in this study is Fadama III. The current Fadama III project is designed to increase the production efficiency of Fadama users (farmers, pastoralists, hunters, among others) and consequently assist on rehabilitation of community owned agricultural infrastructure. It was also designed to increase food security, reduce poverty and contribute to the achievement of a key Millennium Development Goal (MDG). Financing of the Fadama project comprised \$250 million from the World Bank through International Development Agency (IDA) credits and \$200 million counterpart contribution from Nigeria's federal, state and local governments and beneficiaries (Oredipe, 2014). Sadly, most of the government policies on agriculture are characterized by backward flips, lip service, inconsistencies, poor implementations and mismanagement of funds. The Federal and state governments of Nigeria and other multinational organizations like the World Bank, have spent huge sums of money in implementing some agricultural policies, one of which is Fadama III. Unlike the first and second phases of the programmes, the Third National Fadama Programme was designed to accommodate all the states in Nigeria as well as Akwa Ibom State. It is argued that the goals of Fadama III have not been met due to some inadequacies in its implementation. Thus, this study aimed to investigate the effect of Fadama III on rehabilitation of community owned agricultural infrastructure in Akwa Ibom State.

Objective of Study

The objective of this study was to ascertain the impact of Fadama III Project on the rehabilitation of community owned agricultural infrastructure in Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis of the Study

H₀: There is no significant impact of small-scale community-owned infrastructure on rehabilitation of community owned agricultural infrastructure in Akwa Ibom State.

Conceptual Review

Fadama Agricultural Project

The word “Fadama” is a Hausa name for irrigable land which is in flood plains and low-lying areas underlined by shallow aquifers and found along Nigeria's river systems. Fadama areas are typically waterlogged in the rainy season but retain moisture during the dry seasons. These areas are considered to have a high potential for economic development through appropriate investments in productive assets, rural infrastructure and some technical assistance. The desire to harness the vast potential of Fadama in Nigeria culminated in the design of National Fadama Development Projects I, II and III. It is called Fadama in Hausa,

Akuro in Yoruba and “Ude” or 'Ala-mmiri in Igbo. Fadama in Hausa describes irrigable land, usually low-lying plains underlined by shallow aquifers found along Nigeria's major river systems (Blench & Ingawa, 2004). Additionally, the Ibibios in Akwa Ibom State called it “Ibiok” or “Ndioho” or “Edep-asat” (Ekan, Imoh-Ita and Ntuen, 2024).

The World Bank through its Fadama Projects has consistently supported the development of agriculture in a bid to help Nigeria achieve food self-sufficiency in the near future. The Nigerian Government, with the active involvement of the States and Local Governments, initiated quick and sustainable agricultural and rural development projects with a nationwide spectrum targeted at dry season farming activity and related to agro-processing activities (Ovharhe, 2016).

The essence of the National Fadama Development Project (NFDPP) was to ensure all-year-round production of crops, in all the states of the federation through the exploitation of shallow aquifers and surface water potentials in each state using tube wells, wash boreholes and petrol-driven pumps technology. The project was an idea conceived by the World Bank. The programme was projected to last for five years, from 23rd March, 2009 -31st December, 2013. It was a nationwide programme and covered twenty Local Government Areas in each of the thirty-six states of the federation, targeting small-holder farmers involved in pastorals, fisher folks, traders, processors, hunters and gatherers, the disadvantaged and physically challenged. Besides capacity building, the National Fadama Development Project was multidisciplinary in nature, which involved capacity building, communication and information support, asset acquisition and market system development, small-scale community infrastructure (roads, markets, boreholes, culverts, pumps and sprayers), processing and storage centre, advisory services and training. Pertinent about the project was that its services were offered on a grant basis with the Community Driven Development (CDD) principle where the rural farmers determined their needs, and it was all about inclusive (production, processing, marketing, and storage) in areas of agriculture. The project used trained facilitators to ensure that various Economic Interest Groups (EIG's)/Fadama User Groups (FUGs) and Fadama Community Associations (FCA's) were guided (Chukuemeka *et al.*, 2022). The National Fadama Development Project is divided into three phases:

Fadama Phase III: The third phase tagged Fadama III project came fully into operation in 2009 as a follow-up to the Fadama II project which was assessed to have impacted the lives of rural farmers, raising their incomes by 63 per cent (Olaolu *et al.*, 2013). A project like Fadama II took the CDD approach, which places beneficiaries in the driver's seat where local community members under the umbrella of Fadama Community Associations (FCAs and Fadama Users Groups (FUGs) oversee the design and implementation of the project and were empowered through skills and capacity building to improve their livelihoods by increasing income generating activities. Fadama III project established standardized procedures and steps to guide the local people on how to take part in the decision-making process. It established platforms for participation, such as local consultation meetings to identify and select the needed infrastructure to be funded by the project.

Agricultural Infrastructure

Agricultural infrastructural investment has majorly focused on irrigation, transportation, electric power and agricultural markets. However, following the World Bank Report (2009), the definition of agricultural infrastructural infrastructure was narrowed down to comprise long-lived engineered facilities and other services which include roads,

electricity supplies and telecommunication. The relationship between infrastructural development and agricultural productivity can be seen in the fact that Agricultural related infrastructures are expected to reduce farmers' costs and accelerate output and produce more employment opportunities in the agricultural sector. Kikenwa, Abdul-Hammed, Kuye, Business (2017) claims that agricultural productivity is closely is greatly influenced by infrastructure like road, Information and Communication Technology (ICT). A study from Adesina (2017) shows that agricultural output increases with the improvement in the quality of the roads. As further argued by (World Bank, 2018), roads, electricity supplies, telecommunication and other infrastructure are important stimulant to agricultural output, especially in rural areas.

In the past decade, improvement in infrastructural development has been recorded by ECOWAS countries. According to African Development Bank annual report (2016), development in the ICT sector is followed, rather not closely, by growth in the transport sector. Despite this, the current state of road networks in Africa generally, in comparison with other continents of the world shows that Africa continues to lag behind in both availability and quality of road networks. In ECOWAS, two initiatives have been put in place towards improving infrastructure in the region. The first is the Program for Infrastructure Development for Africa (PIDA) designed to support the African Union Abuja Treaty and the Africa Economic Community. The second is the Africa Infrastructure Country Data (AICD) endorsed by New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD), the development banks and several other bodies. The key focus of both programs is to provide new ways and means of putting infrastructure to boost agricultural productivity, create jobs and ignite growth. Through public-private partnership, the ECOWAS infrastructure Projects Preparation and Development Unit (PPDU) on regional infrastructure was also established to ensure that the PIDA initiative was successfully implemented. Despite these measures, basic infrastructures available in ECOWAS countries are still inadequate and have remained behind global performance (Richardson *et al.*, 2020)

Agriculture infrastructural development is used to describe improvement in physical and non-physical infrastructure that is vital to a country's economic development. Infrastructural development is a key driver for economic progress and a critical enabler for productivity (Tunde and Adeniyi, 2012). Economic development theorists have identified infrastructure as critical in agricultural productivity. This implies that the productivity capacity of agriculture depends on adequacy of infrastructure, especially those that aid agricultural productivity.

KIkenwa *et al.* (2017) noted that the relationship between agricultural infrastructural development, agricultural output and agricultural employment continues to attract attention among policy makers. Despite several studies, there is no general consensus regarding the effect of infrastructural development on agricultural output and agricultural employment. The results of previous studies that examined such relationship in developing countries with conflicting results cannot be used to generalize for ECOWAS. Given the huge investment on infrastructural development, it is imperative to evaluate its impact on agricultural output and agricultural employment.

Several studies have examined the influence of infrastructural development on agricultural output and agricultural employment with varying outcomes (Lokesha and Mahesha, 2017) opine that the development of rural infrastructural stimulates agricultural

productivity, economic growth and overall quality of life. Limi, and Smith, (2007) provide evidence that various infrastructure affects agriculture output differently depending on the type of commodity. In a study involving African countries, it was found that transport network is essential in the promotion of cocoa and coffee production. Result depicts that in some countries, a percentage improvement in infrastructure increases growth by about 0.5 percent. In Democratic Republic of Congo, Ulimwengu, Funes, Heady and You, (2009) estimated the impact of road infrastructure on agricultural production and household wealth. The simulation result reveal that road infrastructure improve market access and in turn affect agricultural productivity and household wealth. Manggat, Zain, and Jamaluddin, (2018) examined the impact of transportation infrastructure on agriculture productivity in Ghana using data at a very fine spatial level. The study finds a strong positive effect of railroad on cocoa production.

Fadama 111 and Agricultural infrastructure

Agricultural production, methods of preservation and infrastructure have remained undeveloped despite many years of efforts on technology generation and transfer in Nigeria. Rural financial supports are scarce and the rural finance policies implemented previously have impaired rather than assisted (Simonyan and Omolehin, 2012). However, in an attempt to improve agricultural facilities and alleviate poverty among rural Nigerians and also to increase the incomes and productivity of the rural inhabitants as an approach of meeting up with the millennium development goals (MDGs) of food sufficiency and poverty eradication, the Federal Government of Nigeria through the pooled World Bank loan came up with Fadama project, to finance the development of fadama lands by introducing rehabilitation of community owned agricultural infrastructure and small-scale irrigation in states with fadama development potentials. The project aimed at ensuring that Fadama facilities in Fadama areas are fully utilized to ensure all year round production of crops. Fadama are low laying lands subject to seasonal flooding or water logging along the banks of streams or depressions (Yunana, Abubakar and Francis 2013).

According to Baba and Singh (1998), the fadama lands have high potentials and agricultural values several times more than the adjacent upland. Fadama development is a typical form of farm house and agricultural infrastructure rehabilitation practice characterized by flexibility of farming operations, low inputs requirement, high economic values, and minimal social and environmental impact and hence conform with the general criteria for sustainable development (Akinbile et al., 2006)

The Fadama III projects successfully refined approaches for improved utilization of infrastructure and farm lands. Fadama III is implementing an innovative local development planning (LDP) tool and building on the success of the community-driven development mechanisms. The cumulative impact of these earlier successful Bank-assisted projects attests to the robustness of the small-scale and community based approach to fadama development in an environmentally sensitive manner. According to Yunana, Abubakar and Francis ,(2013) the Fadama III operation supported the financing and implementation of five main components designed to transfer financial and technical resources to the beneficiary groups in: (i) institutional and social development; (ii) physical infrastructure for productive use; (iii) transfer and adoption of technology to expand productivity, improve value-added, and conserve land quality; (iv) support extension and applied research; and (v) provide matching grants to access assets for income-generation and livelihood improvements.

Adeoye *et al.* (2011) undertook a study to examine rural infrastructure and profitability of farmers under fadama III project in Oyo state, using infrastructural index and gross margin. They compared the infrastructural development between fadama III local government areas and non- fadama III areas. Their findings revealed that, more than half of the villages in fadama III local government areas have more infrastructures than non fadama III villages. This implies that Fadama III project had contributed significantly to the development of infrastructures in Oyo state. The cross sectional studies shown above have exposed that society is subject to a process of development, which is itself not arbitrary, but regular.

Yunana, Abubakar and Francis, (2013) noted that Fadama III focus more on agricultural based sub-projects and agricultural infrastructure because the major occupation of the people is in agriculture. This is supported by the fact that Fadama III is a Community Driven Development (CDD) project. The project supported both agricultural and non-farm activities and the demand of the households. Both the agricultural and non-farm activities contribute to the income of the beneficiaries which happens to be one of the objectives of the Fadama III project. They further stated that Fadama III project has succeeded in increasing the value of productive assets and agricultural infrastructure in an attempt to increase the income of the beneficiaries. This is because the value had increased by about 10 times what it was before the project for the Fadama beneficiaries. This is an indication that the issue of productive assets before the Fadama III project was very low compared with what is now on ground just three years after the take-off of the project. This very large increase might be due to the fact that the ownership of such assets was almost nonexistent or very limited before the commencement of Fadama III project. The increase in value of jointly owned productive assets includes the value of the cash transfer from the project to the beneficiaries. When compared to all non-beneficiaries, and non-beneficiaries within and outside communities, the value of privately owned productive assets of Fadama III beneficiaries increased significantly due to participation in the project. It could be noted that even though Fadama III did not interfere with the ownership of the productive assets. This is probably responsible for the significant (5% level) increase in the value of productive assets by the beneficiaries. It could also be as a result of the fact that FUG members were required to buy complementary inputs to support the jointly owned productive assets. The acquisition of productive assets and agriculture infrastructure contribute significantly to increased income of farmers (Yunana, Abubakar and Francis, 2013)

Statistics investigated for fadama users that 29% suggested new technology, 31% suggested adequate funding, 21% suggested improved input supply while, 19% suggested provision of infrastructure. The statistical analysis found that the Fadama III project has greatly reduced beneficiaries' distance and travel time to the nearest community and there has been a great reduction in waiting time for transport and transport fares, relative to households in non-Fadama Coordination areas. It was also evident that household access to productive assets has increased especially for the poorest households, largely because of the subsidy given to finance acquisition of agriculture infrastructure and assets. The income impacts of the project are likely to be higher in the future since the beneficiaries acquired productive assets and infrastructure that are likely to increase their income significantly. The impact of Fadama III project on productive asset and facilities acquisition is large. This is due mainly to cash transfer from the matching funds that the project provides to Fadama user

groups. The large cash transfer might be an important factor that could impede the replication of this success story (Adeolu, and Taiwo, 2004). Generally, the Fadama III project has achieved its goal of increasing the agricultural infrastructure of the beneficiaries. The project has also succeeded in targeting the poor and vulnerable in its productive-asset component, even though that did not appear to increase significantly short-term household incomes among the poorest asset tiercel.

Theoretical Framework

Theory of Change (Results Chain) (1995)

Weiss (1995) popularized the term “theory of change” as a way to describe the set of assumptions that explain both the mini-steps that lead to the long-term goal of interest and the connections between program activities and outcomes that occur at each step of the way. Theory of change is an explicit process of thinking through and documenting how a program or intervention is supposed to work, why it will work, who it will benefit (and in what way) and the conditions required for success.

Theory of change relied on several underlying assumptions. A primary assumption was that Fadama producers were willing to receive agricultural extension advice and adopt innovations. A second assumption was that a pool of knowledgeable agriculturalists, trained as extension officers, was available to mobilize producers and build their capacity, conduct training, and promote the use of advisory tools such as Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and e-extension. A third assumption was that certified input supply agents were available and had the capacity to rehabilitate community own agricultural infrastructure. A fourth assumption was that government would adopt the Fadama III paradigm shift toward local, demand-driven investment and empowerment for rural development, and that the government would enact agricultural policies that supported Fadama III interventions. Given that Fadama was a project in the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD), it was also assumed that strong inter-ministerial coordination would prevail at all levels of government to create synergies and achieve the desired results. Fadama III (Original Project) sought to increase the incomes of rural households (users of rural lands and water resources) by facilitating demand-driven investments and empowering rural community groups to improve productivity and the quality of fadama land, through:

- (i) Financing investments in productive community infrastructure to increase agricultural productivity and diversify sources of livelihood;
- (ii) Building the capacity of community organizations to increase the stock of social capital;
- (iii) Strengthening the capabilities of participating states and local governments to deliver services to the rural poor;
- (iv) Providing advisory services and promoting the adoption of improved technology and good agricultural practices; and
- (v) Promoting socially inclusive and environmentally sustainable management of natural resources.

The interventions supported under Fadama III were expected to lead to increased production; they would also improve prices obtained by crop, livestock, and fish producers by adding value and linking producers to markets - for instance, through off-taker arrangements in which producers formally agreed to supply produce to a buyer, such as an

agribusiness). Through these pathways, agricultural incomes would rise, and the sector would strengthen its contribution to the long-term national objectives of food security, economic growth, and poverty reduction.

Empirical Literature

Research carried out by Amadi *et al.* (2019) titled “Evaluation of National Fadama III Development Project: Cataclysm for Rural Development in Rivers State, Nigeria”, confirmed that agriculture is the bedrock for combating poverty and developing rural areas. The motivation was to reveal the concept, approaches and implementation process of economic interest groups and government financial commitments to various farming activities in local government areas. Materials for the study were provided through secondary sources, Fadama office reports and published materials. The study adopted a descriptive method of analysis. Findings revealed that there are remarkable improvements in rural development in the participating local government areas. The assessment further revealed committed efforts by officers and management of the programme which ensured the effective implementation of rural infrastructure in participating communities. It was recommended that expenditure control measures adopted by the management of the Fadama programme in Rivers State should be applied in future agricultural projects to ensure quality deliverables; the government should pursue only rural development-oriented agricultural policies, and finance projects that have certified Local Development Plans; seeming difficult criterion that delay the release of funds should be relaxed for agricultural programme managers to be proactive to beneficiaries' requests and function effectively. Finally, the Fadama programme should be extended to increase communities' dual opportunities of experiencing both agricultural and rural development.

Madu (2019), conducted in 2018 to assess the effects of Fadama III on rural farmers in Shelleng Local Government Area (LGA), Adamawa State, Nigeria. Sixty women beneficiaries and 60 non-beneficiaries were sampled for the study. Questionnaire was used to obtain information from the respondents on adoption rate of technology, change in income, change in farm size, increase in output and livelihood. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential Statistics. Findings of the research revealed that the adoption of technologies was huge and significant at $P=0.05$ except for water pump and harrowing. The findings also revealed that there was a significant increase in farm size, output and subsequently income at $P=0.05$ among the women beneficiaries compared with non-beneficiaries alike. Also the beneficiaries had better livelihood than the non-beneficiaries in terms consumption expenditure. Contribution to consumption expenditure was significant among the women participants compared to non-participants. In conclusion, Fadama III has made significantly positive impact on the livelihood of the rural women farmers in the study area. It is recommended that credit service providers be involved to help offer credit at competitive interest rates to the poor women using collateral substitutes such as group repayment incentives. The policymakers should as well consider reducing the contribution of the participants from 30% to only 10% in the next phase of the project to enable the poor and vulnerable groups like women, acquire the productive assets like the water pumps.

Similarly, the study conducted to examine the Fadama-III intervention project and its effects on beneficiaries' livelihood in Kware Local Government Area of Sokoto State by Sanusi *et al* (2021). Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the benefiting local

government area and twenty participants were also chosen from the area. The study used both primary and secondary sources of data. Focus Group Discussions (FGD) was used as source for primary data while the secondary data were derived from various secondary sources. The primary data were analyzed thematically, transcribed and presented verbatim in the report. The secondary data were analyzed through content analyses. The study found that, Fadama III intervention project in the study area has significant positive effect on the livelihoods of the beneficiaries such as moderate success in individual ability to own assets. On the contrary, the project has no significant effect on some areas of beneficiaries' livelihoods such as inability to own household assets and ability to participate in social delivery services. Based on these findings, it is recommended that the tentacles of the project be expanded and more strengthened so that more individuals can benefit. Strengthening the scope of the project would go a long way in making the project to empower the beneficiaries so that other aspects of their livelihoods that are yet to be influenced positively would be covered including their educational attainment. Technically, one of the means through which the project could be strengthened is to cancel counterpart funding which has always constitute serious challenge for many poor individuals that want to access the project among others.

Iwala (2014) conducted a study to assess the economic impact, viability and sustainability of the Fadama III sponsored small-scale infrastructure in different communities of Ondo State, Nigeria. Nine Local Government Areas (LGAs) were randomly selected out of the 18 LGAs participating in the project on the basis of 3 LGAs per senatorial district. A total of 270 respondents made up of 180 project participants and 90 non-participants constituted the sample size for the study. Economic impact analysis of the projects showed that the average annual gross margin of beneficiaries (participants) had increased by 28.57 percent in the fourth year of project implementation. The viability analysis revealed that, the net project values (NPVs) of all the projects were positive at 26 percent discount factor, also, their Benefit/Cost Ratios (BCRs) were greater than 1 and the Internal Rates of Return (IRRs) were all above average.

Adeoye *et al.* (2011) also undertook a study to examine rural infrastructure and profitability of farmers under fadama II project in Oyo state, using infrastructural index and gross margin. They compared the infrastructural development between fadama II local government areas and non- fadama II areas. Their findings revealed that, more than half of the villages in fadama II local government areas have more infrastructures than non fadama II villages. This implies that Fadama II project had contributed significantly to the development of infrastructures in Oyo state. The cross sectional studies as shown above have exposed that societies are subject to a process of development, which is itself not arbitrary, but regular; and that no social fact can be really understood apart from its history.

Materials and Methods

The mixed research designs were adopted for the study. The descriptive research design was used in explaining in qualitative forms the major variables of the subject under study and their relationships. The survey research design was used in the collection of data and analysis using the quantitative approach. The population of the study was 2,730. This was the total population of Fadama III Development Programme participants in Akwa Ibom State (Akwa Ibom State Fadama Coordination Office, 2024). A well-structured

questionnaire was used in collecting data for the study. After the return of the questionnaire by the respondents, the data was coded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) with interpretation made using frequency tables and percentages. The simple linear regression analysis was used in testing the hypotheses of the study. Simple linear regression was used to estimate the relationship between two quantitative variables. The sample size of the study was 400. It was determined using the Taro Yamane (n) Formula. The sampling techniques used for this study were the stratified sampling technique and purposive sampling techniques.

Test of Hypothesis

The simple linear regression analysis was used in testing the hypothesis of the study. In simple regression analysis, when the significant value is less than 0.05 at a 95% level of confidence or less than 0.01 at a 99% level of confidence, we accept the Alternative hypothesis (H1) and reject the Null hypothesis (Ho), and vice versa.

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant impact of small-scale community-owned infrastructure on rehabilitation of community owned agricultural infrastructure in Akwa Ibom State.

Using the simple linear regression

Group	N	R Square	df	t calculated	t critical	P value	Decision
Small-scale community-owned infrastructure	354	0.398	352	18.730	1.96	.000	H ₀ : rejected
Rehabilitation of community-owned agricultural infrastructure		.345	353				

Source: Field Survey, (2024)

Decision Rule: Reject the null hypothesis if t calculated is greater than (>) t critical. Accordingly, if the p-value is greater than (>) 0.05, then there is no significant contribution but when the p-value is less than (<) 0.05, there is a significant contribution of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

Interpretation: The regression output table for the last hypothesis presents the result of the impact of small-scale community-owned infrastructure on the rehabilitation of community-owned agricultural infrastructure in Akwa Ibom State. Based on the coefficient of determination (r-square), only 34.5% of the total variation in the rehabilitation of community-owned agricultural infrastructure in Akwa Ibom State was explained by small-scale community-owned infrastructure. The results of the regression also revealed a positive impact of small-scale community-owned infrastructure on the rehabilitation of community-owned agricultural infrastructure in Akwa Ibom State ($\beta = 0.398$, t calculated =18.730, t

tabulated =1.96, $p < 0.05$). Given the above result, the null hypothesis that there is no significant impact of small-scale community-owned infrastructure on the rehabilitation of community-owned agricultural infrastructure in Akwa Ibom State is rejected. Based on the above results, we accept the alternate hypothesis that there is a positive relationship between small -scale community-owned infrastructure and rehabilitation of community owned agricultural infrastructure in Akwa Ibom State.

Discussion of Findings

After the analysis of primary data from the respondents, the finding reveals a significant effect of small-scale community-owned infrastructure on agricultural infrastructure in Akwa Ibom State. The researcher affirms this stance owing to conspicuous strides of the project in the diverse senatorial districts. For instance, in Uyo senatorial district, a cold room was completed and fully operational. Located beside Salem African Church in Nsukara Offot, the project gulped over 1.3 million Naira. Additionally, a palm oil processing factory was constructed for the Nda Nsit Fadama Community Associations (FCAs) in Nsit Atai LGA with N361,000 disbursed. In the same Local Government Area, over 1.4 million Naira was disbursed for the construction of a market which has been completed and fully in use, mostly by the Nda Nsit Fadama Community Associations (FCAs) (Akwa Ibom State Fadama Construction Office Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources, 2024).

In Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District, a palm oil processing plant was completed for the Uforo palm oil processing Fadama User Associations (FUAs). The project cost N480, 520. An aquaculture structure was erected for the Ukoette Fishers Multi-Purpose Cooperatives (MPCs) LTD with N511, 230 disbursed. In Abak LGA, the ThankGod Cassava processing FUA received N482,400 for the building and completion of a Cassava processing plant which has been completed and fully operational. Additionally, the Uforo Oil Palm Fadama User Associations (FUAs) also benefited from the construction of the palm oil processing plant which gulped N260,580 (Akwa Ibom State Fadama Construction Office Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources, 2024).

In Eket Senatorial District, a market was built in Ikot Ekong in Mkpato Enin LGA with N1,000,000 disbursed for the project. The project has been completed and fully in use. In the same LGA, an aquaculture structure was completed for the Nka Uforo Ikot Ekpang Multi-Purpose Cooperative (MPC) Fadama User Associations (FUAs), with N445,230 disbursed. A cool room was also constructed in Ekim area of Eket LGA, with a 6km road construction currently ongoing in Onna LGA (Akwa Ibom State Fadama Construction Office Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources, 2024).

The availability of these projects has eased costs of production and has contributed to higher income levels as well as high productivity levels as earlier affirmed by the participants. Empirically, the finding above is supported by Sanusi & Gado (2021) in their study titled "The Impact of Fadama III Project on Livelihoods in Kware Local Government Area of Sokoto State". In the study, respondents agreed that the Fadama III project had led to the provision of infrastructure for agribusiness, including electrical generator to drive irrigation, pick-up vans for transportation of farm produces, local markets, access roads to farms, and even land ownerships. This findings is affirmed by Adeoye *et al.* (2011) who undertook a study to examine rural infrastructure and profitability of farmers under fadama II

project in Oyo state, using infrastructural index and gross margin. Their findings revealed that, more than half of the villages in fadama II local government areas have more infrastructures than non fadama II villages. This implies that Fadama II project had contributed significantly to the development of infrastructures in Oyo state.

Conclusion

The challenges of food inflation and food insecurity in Nigeria have placed agricultural development at the peak of recent academic studies. With food inflation in the country reaching 35.41% in January 2024, and 64.3 million Nigerians said to be food insecure, agricultural development remains central to other aspects of socio-economic development in Nigeria (Aniagolu, 2024). It is also pertinent to state that over 70% of food products are cultivated in rural areas, which also house 42% of Nigeria's population. The geometric growth in the country's population calls for particular investment in general agricultural development, which is the purpose of the Fadama III project, as well as the research interest of the study.

The Fadama III Project has benefitted various aspects of agricultural development. These include a sustainable increase in the income of rural farmers, an increase in production levels, and the availability of agricultural infrastructure. It was discovered that the small-scale community-owned infrastructure of FADAMA III project has improved agribusiness through the provision of agricultural infrastructure in the selected areas. These include the construction of markets for diverse FUA's, the construction of aquacultural structures, construction of cool rooms, construction of cassava and oil palm processing plants, land acquisition, etc. These infrastructures have aided cultivation and agribusiness, hence, increasing both agricultural yields and reducing costs of production.

Recommendations

- Based on the findings of the paper, it was recommended that:
- i. Akwa Ibom State government should ensure that agricultural infrastructure left uncompleted, abandoned or dysfunctional should be resuscitated and made fully operational to increase the scope and scale of production.

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